

POLYPHEM
THE FUTURE OF SMALL-SCALE CSP PLANTS

POLYPHEM

Small-Scale Solar Thermal Combined Cycle

D5.2 Manufacturing/Installation of the solar receiver

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Background: about the POLYPHEM project

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The POLYPHEM project is a research and innovation action funded by the European Union's H2020 program. It is implemented by a European consortium of 4 research centers and 5 industrial partners. The aim is to increase the flexibility and improve the performance of small solar tower power plants. The concept of POLYPHEM consists in implementing a combined cycle formed by a solarized micro-gas turbine and a Rankine organic cycle machine, with an integrated thermal storage device between the two cycles. The need for cooling is minimal.

Developed from a patented technology by CNRS and CEA, the pressurized air solar receiver is integrated in the micro-turbine cycle. The thermal efficiency targeted for the receiver is 80% with a cost of 400 €/kW. The innovative thermal storage uses a thermal oil and a single thermocline tank with a technical concrete filler material.

The main expected impact of this project is to enhance the competitiveness of low-carbon energy production systems through the technology developed. The expected progress is a better fitting of electricity generation to variable local needs, an overall conversion efficiency of solar energy into electricity of 18% for an investment cost of less than 5 €/W and a low environmental impact. By 2030, the cost of electricity production targeted by the POLYPHEM technology is 165 €/MWh for an annual direct normal irradiation of 2600 kWh/m²/year (North Africa and Middle East) and 209 €/MWh under 2050 kWh/m²/year (Southern Europe). In addition to decentralized power generation, other applications are considered for the deployment of this technology used in poly-generation: industrial heat production, solar heating and cooling, desalination of seawater or brackish water.

A prototype plant of 60 kW_{el} with a thermal storage of 1300 kWh is designed, built and installed on the site of the experimental solar tower of Themis in Targasonne (France). The objective of the project is to validate the technical choices under test conditions representative of actual operating conditions.

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[1] European Directive for Pressure Vessels, EDPV 2014/68/EU.

[2] Alloy 625 data sheet , VDM® alloy 625 (VDM Metals)

[3] Alloy 625 data sheet 2, Haynes® 625 Alloy (Haynes International)

[4] Code de construction Des Appareils à Pression (French Construction Code for Pressure Vessel Manufacturing, CODAP 2010 – Division 2

[5] Alloy 230 data sheet , Haynes® 230 Alloy (Haynes International)

[6] Material data table, Comparative Data HTA Plate Mech V2 (Haynes Int.)

List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

Acronym/abbreviation	Meaning/full text
ASME	American Society of Mechanical Engineers
BSE	Back Scattering Electron
CEA	Commissariat à l’Energie Atomique et aux Energies Alternatives
CIEMAT	Centro de Investigaciones Energéticas, Medioambientales y Tecnológicas
CNRS	Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique
CO	Confidential
CSP	Concentrated Solar Power plant
D	Deliverable
EDS	Energy Dispersive Spectroscopy
EDPV	European Directive for Pressure Vessels
HIP	Hot Isostatic Pressing
HT	High Temperature
OM	Optical Microscopy
PU	Public
SEM	Secondary Electron Microscopy
SS	Stainless steel
TC	Thermocouple
TIG	Tungsten Inert Gas
WP	Work Package

1. INTRODUCTION

In the POLYPHEM project WP5, the components of the prototype CSP will be manufactured and implemented on the existing solar tower research facility Themis (operated by CNRS) in France. This WP is divided in five tasks:

- Task 5.1: Manufacturing/Installation of the thermal storage,
- Task 5.2: Manufacturing/Installation of the Receiver,
- Task 5.3: Installation of the power block: μ GT and ORC-module,
- Task 5.4: Piping, auxiliary and safety components, wiring,
- Task 5.5: Commissioning.

The solar receiver and the gas turbine power block will be placed at the focus in the tower, the thermal energy storage and the ORC-module next to the bottom of the tower. Piping, auxiliary devices and cable connections will be installed according to the plant layout issued in WP4 (Task 4.1). At the end of this WP5, the prototype plant will be commissioned and will be normally ready for experimental operation.

Task 5.2 consists in, firstly, manufacturing the project solar receiver in accordance with the results obtained in WP1. More precisely, the Ni-based alloys selected in task 1.1 will be used for parts in contact with HT air and the detailed design of the receiver comes from the optimization obtained during task 1.2.

2. SOLAR RECEIVER MANUFACTURING

2.1 RECEIVER MODULE MANUFACTURING

2.1.1 Module HIP manufacturing design

In order to match with the design optimization obtained during task 1.2, the solar receiver modules are decomposed in elementary parts as simple as possible using CAD software. The final assembly drawings of the modules is presented on **Figure 1**.

Figure 1: Final assembly drawings of a solar receiver module

The table that could be seen on the top right corner of **Figure 1** summarizes the needs of machined parts to manufacture one module and the alloy used for each reference. At the end, the receiver will be constituted of four modules. In order to reduce the cost of the receiver as much as possible, the parts come from standard semi-finished products as follows:

- Ni-based alloy 230: 3.17mm plate, 9.52mm plate, 25.4mm plate,
- Ni-based alloy 600: 0.6mm plates, 8mm outer diameter x 1mm tubes,
- Cu-based alloy CuA1: 5mm plates.

As the exhaust tube will be removed at the end of the manufacturing process, it is taken from a 6mm outer diameter x 1mm SS alloy 304L tube.

2.1.2 Supply issue

No problem occurred to provide the semi-finished products except for the 8mm outer diameter x 1mm Ni-based alloy 600 tubes. Indeed, seamless tubes are currently used in such HIP manufactured components done at the CEA. However, the supplier benchmark for these parts occurred during the first Covid19 French containment and the CEA usual sub-contractors did not answer the supply demand at all, despite multiple reminders. Thanks to POLYPHEM industrial partners, the CEA obtained quotations:

- Seamless tubes from Germany with high cost and non-compatible delivery date with the manufacturing schedule,
- Welded tubes from Italy with reduced cost but also compatible delivery time.

In order not to delay the receiver manufacturing, the second supply had been selected.

2.1.3 Parts machining

After receiving the material semi-finished products and controlling them, they had been sent to a sub-contractor to perform the forming and the machining steps. Photographs of the module parts can be seen on **Figure 2**.

Figure 2: Elementary solar receiver module parts delivered after forming and machining steps

2.1.4 Cleaning steps

As the module parts are assembled using HIP process, an adequate cleaning procedure has to be carried out in order to prevent diffusion bonding issues. Thanks to the CEA background in HIP technology, a referenced procedure dedicated to the specific alloy types (CO) has been used for the POLYPHEM project. Some photos of this specific step are shown at the top of **Figure 3**. The pictures at the bottom of **Figure 3** show the impact of the cleaning procedure on the Cu-based alloy (CuA1 part surface). One has to keep in mind that the assembly following steps have to be carried out quickly after cleaning, especially due to the use of copper parts (fast oxidation/corrosion in ambient air). At the end of the cleaning steps, the twisted tape inserts are put inside the tubes and pinched to prevent any movement during the assembly.

Cleaning all the parts of one module takes approximately 4h (447 parts, 2 technicians full time and engineer inspection at the end).

Figure 3: Photographs taken during the parts cleaning steps and showing the impact of this step on Cu-based alloy CuA1 parts.

2.1.5 Assembly steps before welding

Figure 4 shows the principal assembly steps done before welding. The first one consists in inserting tubes inside two copper grooved plates and then putting three of these small assembly on each side of the Ni-based alloy U shape plate (alloy 600 tubes protruding only on one side of the copper plates). They are then clamped (**Figure 4 (a)**). This operation is repeated until there is only three rows left. The clamps are moved at the bottom of the assembly as much as possible to leave a maximum free space in the center of the module. The last rows of tubes with their copper plates are then pushed inside the free remaining space using a protective plate and a hammer (small blows) until they touch the clamps. The latter are then removed and the last rows of tubes are put in place with small hammer blows (**Figure 4 (b)**).

The tube plate is put on the side of the modules on which the small tubes do not protrude the copper grooved plates and is kept in place using clamps (**Figure 4 (c)**). All the 189 inner tubes are then pushed from the other side to insert them in the tube plate until the tube end reaches the copper plates. Several other clamps are used during this operation in order to help aligning the small tubes with the tube plate holes. This step is repeated a second time with the other tube plate. At the end, the distance between the surface of the tube plate and the end of the tubes must be the same on each side.

The last step consists in putting the cover plate on which the holding reinforcements and the exhaust tube have been welded (side opposite to the solar flux, **Figure 4 (d)**).

All these preliminary assembly steps take about 4h for each module (2 technicians full time and engineer inspection at the end). The module is now ready to go to the welding step. At this point of the manufacturing process, the module must be handled with care (clamps) in order to prevent part movement (weight of a module approximately 250kg).

Figure 4: Assembly of the constitutive parts of a receiver module after cleaning step

2.1.6 Sealing welds

2.1.6.1 Parts welding

The sealing welds is the most important operation but also the most tricky one for manufacturing a HIP component properly. It must be done with a lot of attention by well-trained staff. It is done using TIG welding equipment and alloy 230W filler material (W for Welding special composition) dedicated to alloy 230 welding but also with other Ni-based alloys. For the modules, 0.9mm and 1.6mm in diameter filler material are used, depending on the part thickness.

The first welding step consists in blocking inner tube movement. To do so, each tube is tag welded on one of the tube plates and the operation is repeated on the other side of the module (**Figure 5 (a)**).

In a second step, the Ni-based alloy plates are preliminary linked together with spaced short length welding beads (**Figure 5 (b)**). In order to prevent too much deformation during the HIP step, several clamps are used to reduce the gap between the parts inside the module as much as possible. The same operation is performed between the plates and the tube plates.

When all the outer parts are blocked thanks to the welding beads, the complete sealing welding of the outer parts is performed (**Figure 5 (c)**).

The final welding step consists in making a complete sealing weld between each inner tube and the tube plate. This welding is very tricky and the procedure has evolved during the manufacturing of the four POLYPHEM receiver modules. The last version and the more effective one is shown on **Figure 5 (d)** (filler material used, welding end far from the tube / tube plate interface, two phases per tube). Indeed, some Ni-based alloys are well known to be sensitive to hot cracks during welding. An example of such defects is visible on **Figure 6** at the end of the welding bead (case of a welding made without caution and without filler material). The evolved welding procedure helps to reduce the number of defects, but not to prevent them completely. After finishing all the inner tube / tube plate welds on one side, a visual inspection is done on each one. If a defect is detected, the weld is repaired by remelting the defect zone using the welding torch (no filler material added). When no more defect is observed, the same final welding step is performed on the other side of the module.

This part of the manufacturing procedure takes approximately one day and a half (1 qualified welder full time and engineer inspection at the end).

Figure 5: Welding steps

Figure 6: Defects observed on inner tube / tube plate welding made without caution (alloy 600 tube on alloy 600 plate without filler material, OM)

2.1.6.2 Leakage detection and repair

When all the welds are finished, a leakage detection is made on the module. This procedure is necessary to insure that the HIP process gas does not enter the module from these potential weak points, which would compromise the component manufacturing. This step implies to connect the exhaust tube on a He detector which makes high vacuum inside the component ($<10^{-2}$ mbar) and detects leakage when spreading He outside the module (Figure 7 (a)).

2.1.6.2.1 First Inner tube / tube plate welding tests

This operation is done with the module in vertical position (Figure 7 (a)). He gas is spread on each weld between a tube and the tube plate at the top of the module independently with a waiting time of approximately 30s before acting:

- If the He leakage rate is still under 1.10^{-9} mbar.L.s⁻¹, the next weld is tested,

- If the He leakage rate rises above 1.10^{-9} mbar.L.s⁻¹, the tested weld is isolated with a patch (**Figure 7 (b)**), sufficient time is let to the He detector to show a leakage rate under 1.10^{-9} mbar.L.s⁻¹, then the next weld is tested.

Figure 7: Leakage detection procedure including repair step

After testing all the welds of the tube plate placed at the top, the leaky ones are repaired by remelting the defect zone using the welding torch (no filler material added, **Figure 7 (c)**). Each repaired weld is then tested independently as before and the repairing operations are done again until the leakage rate stay under the limit of 1.10^{-9} mbar.L.s⁻¹.

2.1.6.2.2 Plate junction tests

Next, the welds between the Ni-based alloy plates are tested when no more leakage is detected on the top tube plate. This step ends when no leakage is detected (leakage rate still under 1.10^{-9} mbar.L.s⁻¹, after He gas aspersion).

2.1.6.2.3 Second tube / tube plate welding tests

The receiver module is then reversed in order to have the second tube plate at the top of the component. The operations made on the first tube plate are then performed on the second one until no leakage is detected.

The leakage detection takes approximately one day using the optimized welding procedure (2 technicians full time and engineer inspection from time to time). For example, this step lasted three days for the first module welded with conventional welding procedure without filler material and weld end at the tube / tube plate junction.

2.1.6.3 Degassing step and exhaust tube tight closure

The module exhaust tube is connected to a high vacuum pumping system in order to degas the inside of the component (**Figure 8 (a)**). This step is considered completed when the vacuum rate read on the gauge is under 1.10^{-6} mbar. It takes approximately 16h to 18h.

Once the previous step is completed, the module exhaust tube is definitively closed from the outer atmosphere using a dedicated procedure (CO) and a special equipment (**Figure 8 (b)**).

The procedure described below (from § 2.1.4 to § 2.1.6) have been successfully done to manufacture the four modules needed for the POLYPHEM solar receiver.

Figure 8: Degassing step and final closure of the module

2.1.7 HIP process

In order to reduce the cost of the HIP step and to be more representative to an industrial manufacturing process of the solar receiver, it has been decided to HIP the four POLYPHEM modules in only one cycle. A special holding tool has been designed, qualified and manufactured by CEA to hold the modules vertically in the HIP furnace (Figure 9 (a)). This special equipment has been shipped with the components on individual holders to the HIP supplier plant to prevent any injury, especially on the exhaust tubes.

Before the HIP process, the four modules have been attached on the holding component and have been equipped with eight measurement TC in order to record the temperature during the cycle (Figure 9 (b)).

Figure 9: HIP process

The HIP step occurred on the 3rd of March 2021 without any problem (cycle conformity according to the quality report, HIP step parameters CO). The only issue encountered was some twisted tape inserts which went out of one module when the latter was lifted from the holding component at the end of the HIP cycle (Figure 9 (c)). This phenomenon occurred only on the first module manufactured (module with the tube / tube plate welds made without filler material). These inserts were put again inside the tubes without any problem.

Figure 10 shows photographs of the exhaust tubes of the four receiver modules. These latter were flattened, a sign that normally the HIP step has been effective (important pressure differential between the HIP furnace and inside the modules).

Figure 10: Exhaust tubes after the HIP process

2.1.8 Tube plate side welding

The final manufacturing step concerning the receiver modules consists in welding the tube plate side. These parts will help to weld the modules one to the other and with the manifolds. These junctions are presented on **Figure 11**.

Figure 11: Welds between modules themselves (red line and curve) and between modules and manifold (blue line and curve)

The procedure to join the sides to the tube plates is listed below:

- The parts are installed on each side of the tubes plates (**Figure 12 (a)**) and hold in place thanks to tag welding.
- A complete welding is done on the outer side of the module (**Figure 12 (b)**). No problem appeared during this step.

- A complete welding is done on the inner side of the tube plate / side assembly. Unfortunately, an issue occurred during this step. Liquid metal was spread during this operation when the weld puddle reached each previous tube / tube plate welds (**Figure 12 (c)**) and stopped when the metal solidified.

Figure 12: Tube plate side welding operations and problems encountered

After the tube plate side welding, more or less large blisters appeared on the insulated surface during handling of the modules (**Figure 12 (b)**). These issues appeared on all four modules.

2.2 ASSEMBLY OF THE RECEIVER MODULES ON THE MANIFOLDS

In parallel with the module manufacturing, actions have been done concerning the design basis for the solar receiver manifolds. A 3D drawing of the final design of the POLYPHEM receiver is shown on **Figure 13**. The length of each manifold is 1.5m long.

Figure 13: Final solar receiver design including the modules (grey parts), the inlet manifold (green parts) and the outlet manifold (blue parts)

2.2.1 Material supply

POLYPHEM solar receiver will be used at very high temperature and is also subjected to the EDPV [1]. Consequently, the material used to manufacture the manifolds (in green and blue, **Figure 13**) has to be referenced in a pressure

vessel code. As alloy 600 is not referenced in any code and has reduced mechanical properties at very high temperature, the Ni-based alloy 625 has been selected. This alloy has a reduced cost compared to alloy 230 and is an approved material of construction under the ASME Boiler and Pressure Vessel Code.

Due to the size of the manifolds, it is only possible to find welded tubes in alloy 625 (not seamless ones). Standard dimensions as close as possible to the expected ones have been selected in order to reduce supply duration:

- Inner manifold : Outer diameter 168.275mm, thickness 10.97mm,
- Outer manifold : Outer diameter 219.075mm, thickness 12.70mm,

For the closing caps and the flanges, the preforms are taken from a 25.4mm thickness plate also in Ni-based alloy 625.

2.2.2 Pressure/temperature working resistance of POLYPHEM Project solar receiver

In order to validate the design of the solar receiver manifolds, studies have been made using fine element simulations. A draft of a complete document has been written as justification for the pressure/temperature working resistance of the POLYPHEM Project solar receiver. Part of this document concerning the EDPV ranking and mechanical criteria is given in **Annex 1**. As problem occurred on the modules (explained in §3), no final version was achieved. The following section presents the main results of these studies.

2.2.2.1 Geometry

As the outlet manifold will be exposed to higher temperatures compared to the inlet one, the studies focused only on this part of the receiver (**Annex 1**). A global view of the modelled assembly is presented on **Figure 14**.

Figure 14: Global view of the modelled assembly

More precisely, the assembly is composed of:

- One Ni-based alloy 625 tube, inner diameter 193.7mm, thickness 12.7mm, total length 1.5m with a machined window with an height of 167mm and a length of 1.21m (**Figure 15 (a)**),
- One Ni-based alloy 625 machined closing cap, outer diameter 219mm, total thickness 25.4mm (**Figure 15 (b)**),
- Two end modules in Ni-based alloy 230 (only the tube plate), length 304mm, height 196mm, with one side thickness of 4.8mm and the other one with a thickness of 1mm (**Figure 15 (c)**),
- Two center modules in Ni-based alloy 230 (only the tube plate), length 304mm, height 196mm, with only one side thickness of 1mm (**Figure 15 (d)**).

The limit conditions are shown on Figure 16:

- Fixed support to simplify the modelling (no movement possible, **Figure 16 (a)**),
- Surfaces on which the air pressure is applied (**Figure 16 (b)**).

Figure 15: Parts composing the modelled assembly with the principal dimensions and materials

Figure 16: Limit conditions: (a) Surfaces where the embedded condition is set, (b) Cross section of the assembly showing the surfaces on which the pressure is applied

2.2.2.2 Pressure and temperature conditions

According to the EDPV [1], pressure/temperature analysis has to be done under working conditions and at room temperature with a pressure adjusted depending on the mechanical properties of the alloys at room and working temperatures. Only the results under working conditions are shown in this section. Results at room temperature are given in **Annex 2**.

Concerning the pressure, the service pressure of the receiver is fixed equal to 2.49 bar (2.5 bar taken into account, **Annex 1**). This pressure is applied on the blue surfaces shown on **Figure 16 (b)**.

For the temperature, the air inside the manifold of the receiver on the outlet side will be at 750°C. One has to know that despite the fact that the insulated temperature of the modules reaches 950°C during operation (POLYPHEM Deliverable D1.2), the outlet manifold is insulated in order to reduce its maximum temperature. Considering this information, the maximum temperature of the manifold and outlet tube is considered at an average level of 870°C (mechanical properties available at this temperature). Moreover, in order to be conservative and to simplify the simulations, the temperature of the outlet manifold is considered as uniform and equal to 870°C.

At high temperature, Ni-based alloy 625 (tube and closing cap) shows the reduced mechanical properties compared to Ni-based alloy 230 (tube plates). According to the EDPV criteria concerning alloy 625 (**Annex 1**), the maximum allowable stress at working temperature will be 109 MPa for the base material and 92 MPa for the welds (welding coefficient of 0.85 compared to base material, **Annex 1**). In the following paragraphs, the VON MISES equivalent stresses are compared to these criteria.

2.2.2.3 Mesh

These simulations are used to give an estimation of the stresses and deformations with a more important accuracy near the welds. For the receiver outlet manifold, these welds are localized as shown on **Figure 17**.

Figure 17: Welds localization on the outlet side of the solar receiver

The assembly is meshed using solid elements. The general size of the elements is fixed at 5mm aside. In order to increase the accuracy of the results at the welds level, the size element is reduced at 0.5mm aside. The model is then made of more than 5,700,000 elements and 8,200,000 nodes for the complete modelled geometry. Some pictures of the mesh can be seen on **Figure 18**.

Figure 18: Pictures of the mesh made on the modelled geometry

2.2.2.4 Strain and stress results under working conditions

The deformation of the assembly under working conditions is shown on **Figure 19** (real deformation). The maximum deformation in this case is very low (21.9 μ m). It is located on the inner surface of the assembly near the weld between a center module manifold and the tube.

Figure 19: Total deformation under working conditions – Cross-section (real deformation) showing the weld between the manifolds and the outlet tube (orange line)

Figure 20 shows the equivalent VON MISES stresses for the complete assembly modelled under working conditions ($T = 870^{\circ}\text{C}$ / $P = 2.5$ bar). The maximum stress is localized at the closing cap and tube junction with $\sigma = 31.9$ MPa. More precisely, the volume of Ni-based alloy 625 near the junction between the tube and the closing cap showing a stress above 15 MPa is very limited (**Figure 21**). The maximum stress level observed is below the stress criteria for the base materials and for the welds in the case of alloy 625 (109 MPa and 92 MPa respectively).

Figure 20: VON MISES equivalent stresses in the complete assembly under working conditions

Figure 21: Volume with VON MISES equivalent stress above 15 MPa, junction between the tube and the closing cap under working conditions

2.2.2.5 Creep

Very limited information is available concerning creep issues in the EDPV [1]. Consequently, the creep evaluation has been done using the French pressure vessel code called CODAP [4]. The paragraph GA5.6.1.b of the CODAP gives the formula to estimate the nominal stress for calculation in a normal service situation including material creep (**Annex 1**).

The creep stress criteria at working temperature will be 6.8 MPa for alloy 625 and 26.9 MPa for alloy 230.

- **Alloy 625 parts**

Zones showing stress above alloy 625 CODAP creep criterion are only visible at the closing plate / tube junction (**Figure 22 (a)**) and at the end module manifold / tube junction at the opposite side of the outlet manifold (**Figure 22 (b)**).

Figure 22: Stresses in alloy 625 parts over CODAP creep criterion (6.8 MPa): (a) near the junction between the outlet tube and the closing cap, (b) along the weld between the tube and the extreme module manifold

Precise examination of the junction between the outlet tube and the closing cap shows that the volume showing creep stress above the alloy 625 creep criterion at 870°C is very small (thickness less than 0.5 mm, **Figure 22 (a)**).

Concerning the junction between the outlet tube and extreme module manifold (\perp to the tube axis), the results show that the volumes with stress between the alloy 625 creep criterion at 870°C (6.8 MPa) and 8.2 MPa are very small width \approx 6 mm but thickness \approx 1.6 mm, **Figure 22 (b)**).

- *Alloy 230 parts*

As shown on **Figure 23**, the stresses evaluated in the alloy 230 parts (module manifolds) are below the alloy 230 creep criterion at 870°C (26.9 MPa).

Figure 23: Stresses in alloy 230 parts over CODAP creep criterion (26.9 MPa)

2.2.3 Conclusions on manifold design

As shown before, the manifold design is suitable for the POLYPHEM solar receiver under working conditions. Some inspections are needed for very long time application due to creep (nearly 10,000h long at very high temperature), but for POLYPHEM Project duration, it is not necessary.

3. SOLAR RECEIVER MANUFACTURING ISSUES

3.1 RECEIVER MODULE ISSUE INVESTIGATION

As explained in **§2.1.8**, issues occurred during the tube plate side welding (liquid metal spread during this operation, more or less large blister appearing after welding). These phenomena appeared on the four modules.

Some tests have been made on one module chosen randomly in order to determine the origin of the gas trapped inside the assembly:

- The first one was to use the TIG torch to melt again one of the tube / tube plate weld in the middle of the tube plate. Again, liquid metal was spread during the operation, new sign of trapped gas. The torch was pulled back quickly during this test in order to leave a hole opened. Using a portable gas analyzer calibrated on argon gas, the exhaust gas was effectively confirmed to be argon gaz.
- The second test was to drill a small hole on the insulated surface of the same module in the middle of the biggest blister observed. When the Ni-based alloy layer was completely perforated, pressured gas went out

from the blister. The gas analysis showed that it was again Argon (Ar). The observation shows also that the Ni-based skin is no longer in contact with the copper parts inside the module.

Consequently, these tests indicate that a leakage occurred during the HIP process allowing the Argon process gas to enter the modules. However, as the module outer surface and the exhaust tubes were deformed at the end of the HIP step, it seems that the leakage was sufficiently low to have an important pressure difference between the HIP furnace and inside the modules.

Complementary tests have been done to localize the leakage inside the same module previously examined. The drilled blister was connected to the He detector (**Figure 24 (a)**). After about 15min, the leakage rate was stable under 1.10^{-9} mbar.L.s⁻¹ without spreading He gas on the module, a sign of a very low leakage (**Figure 24 (b)**). Then, He gas was spread on different points of the module as follows:

- On the tube / tube plate welds: these tightness tests were done on several welds randomly chosen at room temperature and also at high temperature (550°C) using a heat gun (**Figure 24 (a)**). High temperature tests were done in order to know if the leakage appeared only due to heat opening. In both cases, no leakage was detected on the investigated welds.
- Inside the tubes: in this case, it was not possible to spread He gas far from the tube plate as the twisted tape inserts partially block the insertion of the injection nozzle. Despite this fact, He leakage was observed on some tubes tested (**Figure 24 (c)**). However, the rate observed was not quite high (slightly above 1.10^{-8} mbar.L.s⁻¹).

Consequently, it seems that the trapped Ar gas comes from a leakage of the longitudinal weld of one or several tubes during the HIP step. This potential origin could also explain why this issue occurred on the four modules.

Figure 24: Tests to localize the module leakage

3.2 RECEIVER MODULE REPAIRING SOLUTIONS

Due to the project schedule and budget, the manufacturing of new receiver modules using alloy 600 seamless tubes was not possible. Consequently, studies have been launched in order to find repairing solutions. The three most interesting potential repairing processes have been selected and tested.

3.2.1 Solution 1: New HIP step using Cu inserts inside the tubes

The first repairing solution consists in the following steps summarized on **Figure 25**:

- 1- Drilling the tube plate surface in order to erase the tube / tube plate welds and to extract the twisted tape inserts. This step could also help to extract part of the trapped gas,
- 2- Cylindrical copper rod insertion inside all the empty tubes,

- 3- Welding of closing plates on each tube plates (stainless steel), one with an exhaust tube in order to make an appropriate vacuum inside the modules. This step is finished by a final closure after an adequate degassing step,
- 4- New HIP cycle identical to the previous one done on the modules,
- 5- Drilling the closing plates on each side to reveal the Cu inserts,
- 6- Chemical dissolution of the Cu inserts,
- 7- Old swirls insertion in the tubes or new ones if the old swirls are not reusable.

Despite the first step concerning the insert extraction, this solution has the advantage to be quite simple. Indeed, each step has been previously done independently in previous other manufacturing in the CEA laboratory. Due to the use of massive rods inside the tubes, this solution would lead to reduced module deformation, if it is possible to put Cu rods with outer diameter very close to the tubes. This is a low-risk solution, as it uses a solid-state process.

However, this solution has some disadvantages listed below:

- The supply of more than 756 $\varnothing 6\text{mm}$ L1.02m Cu rods for more than 200kg, which probably need to be machined in order to fit the tube geometry (deformation due to HIP step). This implies a none negligible cost,
- The extraction of the twisted tape inserts. If only one of them is impossible to extract, the repair failed,
- The real geometry of all the inside tubes due to the module deformation after the new HIP step, depending on the size of the Cu rods,
- The insertion of old and new inserts in the modules after the second HIP step, as it is impossible to predict the new tube geometry.

Figure 25: Repairing solution 1, process with new HIP step using Cu inserts inside the tubes

3.2.2 Solution 2: New HIP step using ceramic powder inside the tubes

The second repairing solution consists in the following steps summarized on **Figure 26**:

- 1- Drilling the tube plate surface in order to erase the tube / tube plate welds and to extract the twisted tape inserts. This step could also help to extract part of the trapped gas,
- 2- Filling all the empty tubes using ceramic powder (alumina, no sinter of the powder at the HIP step temperature),
- 3- Welding of closing plates on each tube plates (stainless steel), one with an exhaust tube in order to make an appropriate vacuum inside the modules. This step is finished by a final closure after an adequate degassing step,

- 4- New HIP step identical to the previous one done on the modules,
- 5- Drilling the closing plates on one side to reveal the ceramic powder,
- 6- Removal of the ceramic powder from the tubes,
- 7- Drilling the closing plates on the other side,
- 8- Old twisted tape inserts put again inside the tubes or new ones if the old swirls are not reusable.

Compared to the first solution, this second one has the advantage of requiring ceramic powder (alumina) rather than Cu machined rods. Consequently, the cost is reduced and the filling simpler because it is less dependent of the tube deformation. As the previous one, this is a low-risk solution as it uses a solid-state process.

This second solution shows also disadvantages:

- Filling powder inside the tubes and vibrate the module to have sufficient density (module's weight nearly equal to 250kg),
- As the first solution, the extraction of the inserts. If only one of them is impossible to extract, the repair failed,
- The powder extraction after the new HIP step,
- The tube deformation during the new HIP step (maximum density of the powder equal to 66% of a massive part with an equal volume),
- The insertion of old and new inserts in the modules after the second HIP step, as it is impossible to predict the new tube geometry.

Solution 2: New HIP step using ceramic powder inside the tubes

Figure 26: Repairing solution 2, process with new HIP step using ceramic powder inside the tubes

3.2.3 Solution 3: Copper fusion step and new HIP step

The third and last repairing solution is summarized on **Figure 27** and bellow:

- 1- Drilling the Ni-based alloy plate showing blisters (insolated surface). This step could also help to extract part of the trapped gas,
- 2- Welding a new insolated plate on the module with exhaust tubes (new flat insolated surface),
- 3- Copper fusion treatment in a high vacuum furnace,
- 4- Tightness test, degassing step and final closure of the exhaust tubes,
- 5- New HIP step identical to the previous one done on the modules,
- 6- Cutting of the exhaust tubes and welding of small Ni-based alloy pins (on the previous exhaust tube location to prevent direct contact of copper with air).

This last repairing solution is the simplest one as it involves a minimum operation number on the modules (no tube plate drilling, insert extraction and put back into place).

However, the risks of applying this solution are numerous:

- Risk of Ni-based tube erosion due to Cu liquid phase (the thinnest Ni-based alloy parts), which could lead to copper leakage out of the modules,
- Cu conductivity reduction due to Ni dissolution in particular. For comparison, pure Cu has a thermal conductivity up to $400 \text{ W.m}^{-1}.\text{K}^{-1}$ and copper alloy containing 10% in mass of Ni has a thermal conductivity of $40 \text{ W.m}^{-1}.\text{K}^{-1}$,
- Difficulties to insure the total fusion of Cu inside the modules during the heat treatment (step 3, **Figure 27**),
- Need of tools to prevent module deformation during fusion heat treatment (more than 200kg of liquid Cu per module).

Solution 3: Copper fusion step and new HIP step

Figure 27: Repairing solution 3, process with copper fusion step and new HIP step

3.3 PRELIMINARY TESTS TO CHOOSE THE MOST SUITABLE REPAIRING SOLUTION

In order to test the three repairing solutions, representative mock ups have been manufactured. The parts are extracted from additional spare parts coming from receiver module manufacturing (**Figure 28 (a)** for the tube plates and **(b)** for the copper grooved plates) and from clippings (inside tubes and outer Ni-based alloy plates). The objective is to design mock-ups big enough to contain several tubes but small enough to enter the HIP furnace of the Grenoble CEA center in order to prevent extra cost and delays (1 mock-up treated per cycle). The final assembly drawings of these representative mock-ups for the repairing tests are shown on **Figure 29**.

Figure 28: Representative test mock-up parts coming receiver parts: (a) tube plates, (b) copper grooved plates

Figure 29: Final assembly drawings of a representative mock-up for the repairing tests

The manufacturing steps of the representative mock-ups are exposed on **Figure 30** (after the part cleaning steps). For only one mock-up (the one dedicated to test solution 1), twisted tape inserts have been put inside the tubes during the manufacturing procedure. After the final HIP step, the three mock-ups are considered in the same condition as the scale 1 modules (flattened exhaust tubes).

The test of melting again one of the tube / tube plate weld with a TIG torch was done in the middle of the tube plate for one of the mock-up to verify if HIP process gas was trapped as for the modules. However, this test was negative (no liquid metal spread).

Figure 30: Representative test mock up manufacturing steps

Before operating the repairing solutions on the representative mock-ups, other simple tests have been made to set some manufacturing parameters. The following paragraphs explain the work done to test each solution (§3.3.1 to §3.3.3). The conclusions are explained in §3.3.4.

3.3.1 Solution 1: New HIP step using Cu inserts inside the tubes

The first investigation performed on the representative mock-up was to verify the extraction of the inserts. All the tube / tube plate welds were machined in order to remove the excess filler material, as shown on **Figure 31**. Making chamfers compared to drilling each tube end was preferred in order to reveal the tube / tube plate interface and potentially extract trapped gas (§2.1.8). The removal of the twisted tape inserts was done easily in this case.

Figure 31: Machining of the representative mock-up and insert extraction

In a second step, tests of introducing rods inside the tubes were done using different diameter in order to evaluate the most appropriate one. It appeared that, due to the mock-up deformation, only 5.8mm diameter rods could enter all the tubes. This size was selected for the test of this repairing solution.

The complete repair procedure for Solution 1, performed on the representative mockup, is shown on **Figure 32**. Except the fact that some Cu insert set up requested the use of a hammer, all the repairing steps were done as expected. At

the end of the process, the geometrical examination showed a maximum deformation of 1.5mm localized in the middle of the mock-up. This deformation is due to the gap between the tubes and the inserts filled during the HIP step.

Figure 32: Test of repairing solution 1 (copper inserts) using the representative mock-up

3.3.2 Solution 2: New HIP step using ceramic powder inside the tubes

Before testing the Solution 2 on the representative mock-up, simple mock-ups were designed in order to verify the ceramic powder extraction after the repairing HIP step. These mock-ups are made of a small length of alloy 600 tube (clippings from receiver module manufacturing) filled with alumina powder. This test is considered as conservative situation. Indeed, the deformation of the tube surface would be more important in this case compared to the modules.

Figure 33 shows pictures of the small mock-up manufacturing and the results obtained.

Figure 33: Manufacturing of simple mock-ups for ceramic powder extraction tests

As expected, two of the three mock-ups manufactured presented an important deformation. However, for the third one, only small deformation was observed on the surface, a sign of a HIP gas leakage (**Figure 33 (d)**). Examinations showed that some defects were visible along the longitudinal welding of the tube but it is not possible to confirm that they were at the origin of the leakage. In all cases, it appears that this phenomenon can be related to the issue encountered on the receiver modules: the longitudinal tube weld resistance during the HIP step.

Concerning the deformed mock-ups, one of them was selected and the closing plate was drilled to try to extract the powder. With an initial diameter of 3mm, the powder extraction was impossible. The same result was obtained when increasing the hole diameter up to 6mm (**Figure 34**). It seems that the test was too conservative and the ceramic grains were blocked due to the tube deformation.

Figure 34: Ceramic powder extraction test

Despite the problems encountered with the small mock-ups, it was decided to test the second repairing solution on the representative mock-up. All the steps involved in this test are presented on **Figure 35**. Unfortunately, it was impossible to extract the powder from the inside tubes as for the small mock-ups. The geometrical examination showed a maximum deformation of 2mm localized in the middle of the mock-up, which is due to the powder compaction during the HIP step.

Figure 35: Test of repairing solution 2 (ceramic powder) using the representative mock-up

3.3.3 Solution 3: Copper fusion step and new HIP step

The goals of the first part of this study were:

- To determine the parameters of the fusion step of the third repairing solution, by verifying the complete fusion of the copper parts, the good wetting of the Ni-based parts by the fused copper,
- The potential Ni-based parts erosion due to contact with liquid copper.

As the thinnest layer of Ni-based alloy in the module is the inside tube wall, the small mock-ups were designed with a small part of receiver alloy 600 tube welded on a stainless steel box containing Cu parts (**Figure 36 (a)**). After the fusion test (example on **Figure 36 (b)**), each sample was cut and polished in order to make OM for microstructural observations and SEM for chemical composition (EDS analysis).

Figure 36: Small mock-up to establish fusion step parameters

The results obtained on the initial copper part and on the mock-ups tested near 1100°C for different durations are summarized on **Figure 37**. The characterization of the initial Cu part was carried out as a blank test concerning the EDS analysis when it is focused on only the elements Cu, Ni, Cr and Fe. In this case, the results show only 100% of Cu as expected (**Figure 37 (a)**).

For a fusion test in the range [1093°C-1096°C] during 5 min (**Figure 37 (b)**), the results show that copper fusion has occurred (as some contraction cavities are observed), but also that the fusion is not complete (remaining holes detected between the tube and the copper parts and at the bottom welding). The low tube thickness reduction confirms this result as the composition of the copper phase, with very low dissolution of Ni, Cr and Fe. As a conclusion, 5 min in this temperature range is too short for the fusion step.

For a longer time in the range [1093°C-1100°C] (32min, **Figure 37 (c)**), the copper fusion is more homogeneous (more contraction cavities and no remaining holes visible). However, alloy 600 tube shows an important thickness reduction due to the contact with liquid copper (reduction of ≈36%). Therefore, the copper phase is richer in Ni, Cr and Fe elements, which would affect the thermal conductivity (not evaluated). Consequently, 30min fusion step in the temperature range [1093°C-1100°C] seems to be sufficient for the small mock-up dimensions. However, it has been decided that it would be too short to obtain the same results on the POLYPHEM modules due to their size.

For a test of 1h in the range [1093°C-1100°C] (**Figure 37 (d)**), the tube thickness eroded by the fused copper phase is a little bit higher compared to the test lasting 32min at the same temperature but very close. This result is confirmed by the chemical analysis, which shows a little increase in Ni and Cr in the copper alloy compared to the previous case. These conditions for the fusion step have been selected to realize the test of the third repairing solution on the representative mock-up.

For comparison, a fusion test was done at higher temperature (range [1136°C-1139°C]) for a duration of 37min. As shown on **Figure 38**, the temperature was too high and the duration too long. Indeed, these fusion parameters leads to a complete dissolution of the alloy 600 tube and a liquid copper leakage during the test near the tube / box welding. Another consequence is an important increase of Ni, Cr and Fe in the copper phase. This result indicates that the parameter window above copper temperature (1083°C) is very restricted to correctly perform the fusion step without copper leakage.

(a) Initial Cu Part

Chemical composition (Energy Dispersive Spectroscopy (EDS), % mass, all pink rectangle)
 Cu = 100%
 Ni = 0%
 Cr = 0%
 Fe = 0%

(b) [1093°C-1097°C]/5min

Recorded temperature during fusion test

Chemical composition (EDS, % mass, all pink rectangle)
 Cu = 99.91% Ni = 0.02%
 Cr = 0.02% Fe = 0.01%

→ Time too short to have good Cu/Ni based alloy junctions

(c) [1093°C-1100°C]/32min

Recorded temperature during fusion test

Chemical composition (EDS, % mass, all pink rectangle)
 Cu = 95.27% Ni = 2.25%
 Cr = 0.85% Fe = 1.73%

→ Enough duration to have good Cu/Ni based alloy junctions → time too short for scale 1 modules

→ Quite important thickness reduction and Cu alloy composition impact on conductivity?

(d) [1093°C-1100°C]/1h

Recorded temperature during fusion test

Chemical composition (EDS, % mass, all pink rectangle)
 Cu = 94.84% Ni = 2.58%
 Cr = 0.96% Fe = 1.62%

→ Enough duration to have good Cu/Ni based alloy junctions → enough duration for scale 1 modules

→ Quite important thickness reduction and Cu alloy composition impact on conductivity?

Figure 37: Characterization of the initial Cu parts and results of fusions tests at 1100°C

Figure 38: Results of the fusion test above 1100°C

The third repairing solution involving a copper fusion step was done on the last representative mock-up. As shown on **Figure 39**, the repairing procedure was stopped just after the fusion step due to several issues:

- Firstly, liquid copper went out of the mock-up by the exhaust tube during this step. This tube was kept open in order the evacuate potentially trapped HIP process gas. This phenomenon was not anticipated, as no data is available concerning the liquid Cu thermal expansion coefficient,

Figure 39: Test of repairing solution 3 (copper fusion) using the representative mock-up

- Secondly, copper was observed inside one tube of the mock-up. As copper was not found from the entrance of the tube to approximately 1 cm deep inside the tube on each side of the mock-up (**Figure 39 (d)**). This copper leakage is independent from the exhaust tube issue. The likeliest hypothesis to explain this phenomenon is the presence of one or several defects along this tube especially that enables liquid copper to erode completely the tube more quickly, which leads to the leakage observed. These weak points would be potentially identical to the ones that lead to a HIP gas leakage concerning the modules.

3.3.4 Repairing solution test conclusions

Concerning the first repairing solution (copper inserts), the tests done show that in general, this repairing solution is viable. However, some adjustments are needed if it is applied on the receiver modules:

- As some difficulties appeared during Cu insert set up, the conclusion is that scale 1 inserts must not be 1m long rods but rather small length ones to prevent blocking issues,
- As a significant deformation appeared on the representative mock-up, this phenomenon would be accentuated on the modules. Consequently, it may not be possible to reuse the old twisted tape inserts. Tests would be done after the repairing HIP step to check this point especially and to machined new inserts with adequate diameter if necessary.

Concerning the second repairing solution (ceramic powder), the latter is considered as not viable as all the tests have shown that it is not possible to extract the powder after the HIP step. This solution is abandoned.

Concerning the last solution (copper fusion), the liquid copper leakage from the exhaust tube is not a real problem. Indeed, the goal of these tubes is initially to help removing gas trapped during the first HIP step. As the insulated face of the modules would be replaced during this repairing solution (**Figure 27**), it is expected that most of the trapped gas would be evacuated. Consequently, only one exhaust tube would be used to make vacuum between the new insulated surface and the module and would be tightly closed before the fusion step. However, as a Cu leakage has been observed inside a tube of the representative mock-up (due to tube defect with high probability), it appears that this last solution is not viable for repairing the POLYPHEM modules. Reducing the fusion step duration to prevent such a problem on the modules should lead to an incomplete fusion in the middle due to their size. This solution is abandoned too.

3.4 APPLYING REPAIRING SOLUTION ON THE RECEIVER MODULES

As the only solution viable to repair POLYPHEM receiver is the one involving Cu inserts, the first step done on the modules was to extract the twisted tape inserts.

The job was focused on the first module on which the tube / tube plate welds were made without filler material (no excess material that would block twisted tape insert extraction), allowing to extract the swirls without previous machining step. Almost all the inserts were extracted quite easily from the modules, except the following ones (**Figure 40**):

- The ones welded with the tubes,
- The ones localized in the corner of the tube plate.

For the first ones, as planned in the repairing solution process, a machining step is needed to remove the welding. However, this step must be done with caution especially for these tubes in order to erase the welds without deforming the insert.

The real issue appears for the corner tubes. Several tests have been done to try to extract the twisted tape inserts without success (maximum length extracted \approx 200 mm). It appears that these inserts are blocked far from the tube plate due to the module deformation.

Figure 40: Twisted tape inserts blocked inside the modules

After discovering this new problem, several alternative scenarios have been proposed to cope with it but none of them is acceptable to achieve the receiver repair:

- *Keeping tubes with the blocked swirls without massive inserts during the repairing HIP step:* this scenario would lead in the best case to non-predictable deformations of the module. Consequently, the swirls insertion would be potentially impossible leading to inadequate operating conditions (heat exchange and pressure drop too low). In the worst case, it would lead to the rupture of the structure. In all cases, the modules would not be usable.
- *Patching definitively the problematic holes with powder (mixing copper inserts in the empty tubes and filling of ceramic or metallic powder in the others):* due to the presence of the swirls, powder filling would be difficult, as the latter should block the powder flow. This would lead to an incomplete tube filling and to the same consequences as the first scenario.

Taking into account all the elements listed above, the CEA has decided that the POLYPHEM solar receiver modules are unfortunately irreparable and not to deliver them.

3.5 CONSEQUENCES OF USING NOT REPAIRED SOLAR RECEIVER

One can question what the consequences of using the solar receiver modules with their defects might be, as all the potential repairing solutions are not possible. The major risks are listed and their consequences detailed in the following paragraphs.

3.5.1 Risk of fusion of parts of the receiver

As quite large blisters are located on the insulated surface, separating the Ni-based alloy skin from the copper parts inside the modules, it would be necessary to increase the solar flux on the receiver to balance the important thermal resistance and to reach the adequate outlet temperature needed by the micro-gas turbine. According to the results of the thermohydraulic simulations, in a normal use of the receiver done during POLYPHEM task 1.2 (D1.2), the insulated surface will reach a maximum temperature of approximately 950°C. If the solar flux is highly increased to compensate the thermal resistance, the temperature of the Ni-based skin may reach locally its fusion temperature (1301°C-1371°C

for alloy 230). This would lead to expose inside copper to air at very high temperature and the loss of the receiver. This phenomenon would be increased because of potential incorrect junction between the tubes and the copper matrix (thermal resistance increase).

3.5.2 Risk of complete Ni-based alloy skin / copper parts separation

Another important fact is that the modules contain trapped gas. Consequently, increasing the temperature of the receiver modules implies increasing the pressure of the inside gas implying:

- The blister size increase, which could lead to a complete separation of the Ni-based alloy skin and the copper parts,
- The increase of the insulated surface temperature due to the lack of heat extraction (up to metallic part fusion as the previous case),
- The impossibility to reach the temperature needed to operate the micro-gas turbine.

4. CONCLUSIONS ON SOLAR RECEIVER MANUFACTURING

The POLYPHEM solar receiver was assembled without any significant problem and at first glance, the modules have been HIP treated properly. Some adjustments were needed to reduce the tube / tube plate weld defects and consequently the time needed to verify the tightness of the modules during their assembly.

In parallel to the receiver module manufacturing, a detailed study was made to design and verify the Pressure / Temperature resistance of the receiver in link with the EDPV and French Construction Code for Pressure Vessel Manufacturing CODAP taking into account creep aspects. The conclusion of this study is that the final design of the entire receiver will sustain the nominal working conditions without any problem.

However, problems occurred during the final step of the receiver manufacturing process. The investigations have shown that a gas leakage occurred during the HIP step leading to the formation of defects inside the modules. After several tests, it appeared that the origin of the problem came from the alloy 600 tube supply that have not sustained the HIP step properly (welded tubes compared to seamless tubes often used in HIP manufacturing at the CEA).

In order to try to save the receiver modules, an important study has been conducted to find potential repairing solutions and to test them on mock-ups. Unfortunately, two solutions were abandoned due to issues during the tests on representative mock-ups and the third one, more promising, could not be applied to the modules, as one of the preliminary step was not possible. The CEA decided to stop the repairing tests and consequently, not to supply the POLYPHEM solar receiver.

*Annex 1: Pressure Vessel analysis concerning the solar receiver - EDPV ranking and mechanical criteria***1. UNITS**

The units used in the document are based on International System.

2. WORKING CONDITIONS**2.1 FLUID**

The fluid used inside the receiver is air. According to the EDPV [1], the fluid is from group 2.

2.2 SERVICE PRESSURE

The maximum pressure applied inside the receiver will be 3.32 bar. As the atmospheric pressure at the place where it will be operated is approximately 0.83 bar (THEMIS Tower), the service pressure of the receiver is set at $3.32 - 0.83 = 2.49$ bar (2.5 bar taken into account).

2.3 SOLAR RECEIVER VOLUME

As shown on **Figure 41**, the complete solar receiver is constituted of four identical modules, of one approximately DN150 inlet tube (inside diameter 146.4mm, thickness 11mm) and one approximately DN200 outlet tube (inside diameter 193.7mm, thickness 12.7mm). According to the EDPV [1], the receiver is referenced as an assembly of four pressure vessels (the four modules) and piping (the inlet and the outlet tubes).

Figure 41: Composition of the complete solar receiver: four modules, one inlet tube and one outlet tube

- *Receiver modules:*

As mentioned before, each module is considered an independent pressure vessel. As presented on **Figure 42**, a module is made of $7 \times 27 = 189$ tubes with an internal diameter of 6mm and a length of 1.02m. Each tube contains in its entire length a twisted tape insert made of twisted metal strip with a width of 6mm and a thickness of 0.6mm.

Figure 42: Composition of a solar receiver module to estimate internal volume

First, the calculations to obtain the volume of one internal tube containing an insert are presented in Table 1.

	Internal diameter (mm)	Cross section (mm ²)	Total cross section (mm ²)	Tube length (mm)	Air volume per tube (mm ³)	Air volume per tube (L)
Internal tube	6	28.27	24.67	1020	25167.82	0.025
	Width (mm)	Thickness (mm)				
Insert	6	0.6	3.6			

Table 1: One internal tube with insert volume calculation

As one module contains 189 tubes, the total volume of the tubes with inserts is 0.025 x 189 = 4.757L.

The volume of the manifolds is estimated using the CAD files. For the inlet side, the volume is approximately 0.774L. On the outlet side, it is about 0.69L.

Consequently, the total volume of a receiver module is 6.221L (6.5L taken into account for the calculations).

- Inlet and outlet tubes:

As mentioned before, the complete solar receiver is an assembly and the tubes are taken as piping. As the outlet tube has a larger diameter than the inlet one with the same operating pressure (pressure drop inside the receiver neglected), only the inner diameter of the outlet pipe is important for the rest of the document: DN194.

2.4 SERVICE TEMPERATURE

Concerning the operating temperatures, Figure 43 summarizes the principal operating conditions for the solar receiver in nominal conditions.

Figure 43: Thermal information concerning the receiver during nominal operation conditions

As the air temperature on the inlet side is low and the tube diameter is the smaller one, only the outlet side is investigated. The air temperature inside the receiver on the outlet side will be at 750°C. One has to know that despite

the fact that the insulated temperature of the modules reaches 950°C during operation, the outlet manifold and the tube are insulated in order to reduce their maximum temperature. Considering this information, the maximum temperature of the manifold and outlet tube is considered as less than 870°C. In order to be conservative and to simplify the following part of the report, the temperature of the outlet manifold and tube is considered as uniform and equal to 870°C.

3. EDPV RANKING

3.1 RECEIVER MODULES

The EDPV ranking of a solar receiver module is defined using the table (Table 2) and the Pressure-Volume diagram below (Figure 44).

Technical requirements	
Equipment type	Pressure vessel
Physical nature of the internal fluid	Gas
Danger level of the internal fluid	Group 2 (non-dangerous)
Characteristics in service of the equipment	
Maximum service pressure PS (bar)	2.5
Volume V (L)	6.5
PS.V (bar.L)	16.25

Table 2: Data table for ranking according to EDPV [1] in the case of a solar receiver module

Figure 44: Receiver module ranking according to the EDPV [1] in the case of a pressure vessel using group 2 gas

The working point of the module is indicated using an orange cross in **Figure 44**. The receiver modules are then related to the article 4§3 of the EDPV [1]. They shall be designed and manufactured in accordance with the sound engineering practice of a Member State in order to ensure safe use.

3.2 OUTLET TUBE

The piping ranking of the outlet tube is defined using the table (**Table 3**) and the Pressure-Nominal Diameter diagram below (**Figure 45**).

Technical requirements	
Equipment type	Piping
Physical nature of the internal fluid	Gas
Danger level of the internal fluid	Group 2 (non-dangerous)
Characteristics in service of the equipment	
Maximum service pressure PS (bar)	2.5
Nominal Diameter (DN)	194
PS.DN (bar.mm)	485

Table 3: Data table for ranking according to EDPV [1] in the case of outlet tube

Figure 45: Receiver module ranking according to the EDPV [1] in the case of piping using group 2 gas

The working point of the module is indicated using an orange cross in **Figure 45**. The outlet tubes are then related to the article 4§3 of the EDPV [1]. They shall be designed and manufactured in accordance with the sound engineering practice of a Member State in order to ensure safe use.

4. CODAP CONSTRUCTION CATEGORY

For the pressure vessel responding to the EDPV [1], the manufacture category is determined according to **Table 4**, taken from the paragraph GA5 of the CODAP [4].

Evaluation globale des facteurs potentiels de défaillance et des conséquences d'une défaillance éventuelle	Catégorie de construction <i>minimum</i> des appareils entrant dans le champ d'application de la Directive Européenne Équipements Sous Pression 97/23/CE ou de sa transposition en droit national				
	Sans catégorie	Catégorie de risque I	Catégorie de risque II	Catégorie de risque III	Catégorie de risque IV
Faible	B2	B2	B2	B2	B2
Moyenne	B2	B2	B2	B2	B1
Importante	B2	B2	B2	B2	A
Très importante	B2	B2	B2	B1	A

Table 4: Determination of the manufacture category of pressure vessels, table GA5.4-1, CODAP [4]

As the solar receiver is a prototype intended for experimental tests, the manufacture category B2 is selected (failure factors and associated consequences of medium type, pressure vessel without risk category). However, the CODAP [4] paragraph GA5.4-1 specifies that the rank level must be overvalued if the pressure vessel works in the creep domain (cf. § taken from CODAP [4], **Figure 46**).

Les appareils de catégorie de construction B2, mais destinés à être exploités dans le domaine du fluage doivent être soumis à l'intégralité des exigences de la catégorie B1.

Figure 46: Part of §GA5.4-1 of the CODAP [4] concerning pressure vessels used in the creep domain

Consequently, the manufacture category of the receiver is elevated from B2 to B1. According to Table GA5.4-2 from CODAP [4] (**Table 5**). In order to simplify the calculations, the welding coefficient $z = 0.85$ is applied for all the welding made between the modules and the tubes.

	Catégorie de construction			
	A	B1	B2	
Contrainte nominale de calcul : f	f_1	f_1	f_1	
Coefficient de soudure : z	$z = 1$	$z = 0,85$	$z = 0,85$	

Table 5: Nominal stress for calculations and welding coefficient, Table GA5.4-2, CODAP [4]

5. MATERIALS

The solar receiver is made using alloy 625 (inlet and outlet tubes) and alloy 230 (module manifolds). It is summarized on **Figure 47**.

Figure 47: Alloys used in solar receiver manufacture

5.1 ALLOY 625

The physical and mechanical characteristics of alloy 625 come from manufacturer technical data sheet [2]. The relevant properties are summarized in **Table 6**.

Alloy 625 properties

Room temperature – 22°C			
Density	ρ_{600}	8.47	T.m ⁻³
Young modulus	E	208200	MPa
Yield Strength	R _{p0.2}	417	MPa
Tensile Strength	R _m	894	MPa
Elongation	A%	48	%
Poisson's Ratio	ν	0.32	-
Working temperature – 870°C			
Young modulus	E	146200	MPa
Yield Strength	R _{p0.2}	211	MPa
Tensile Strength	R _m	262	MPa
Elongation	A%	116	%
Poisson's Ratio	ν	0.329	-

Table 6 : Relevant physical and mechanical properties of alloy 625 [2] [3]

5.2 ALLOY 230

The physical and mechanical characteristics of the alloy 230 come from manufacturer technical data sheet [5] and data file [6]. The relevant properties are summarized in **Table 7**.

As the density of alloys 625 and 230 are not available at the working temperature (870°C), the density at room temperature (22°C) will be used (conservative calculations).

Alloy 230 properties

Room temperature – 22°C			
Density	ρ_{230}	8.97	T.m ⁻³
Young modulus	E	214000	MPa
Yield Strength	R _{p0.2}	396	MPa
Tensile Strength	R _m	865	MPa
Elongation	A%	50	%
Poisson's Ratio	ν	0.32	-
Working temperature – 870°C			
Young modulus	E	157200	MPa
Yield Strength	R _{p0.2}	257	MPa
Tensile Strength	R _m	435	MPa
Elongation	A%	65	%
Poisson's Ratio	ν	0.35	-

Table 7 : Relevant physical and mechanical properties of alloy 230 [5] [6]

6. CRITERIA

6.1 DEFINITION

The paragraph C10.2.7 of the CODAP [4] gives admissibility criteria on stresses as follows:

- General primary membrane stress: $P_M \leq f$
- Local primary membrane stress: $P_L \leq 1.5 \times f$
- Total Primary stress (membrane + bending): $P_P \leq 1.5 \times f$
- Resulting stress (primary + secondary): $P_R \leq 3 \times f$

These stresses are TRESCA equivalent ones with f the nominal stress for calculation, which is equal to (Nickel and Nickel-based alloys (M12 materials), CODAP [4]):

Normal working situation: $f = \text{MIN}\{R_{p0.2} / 1.5; R_m / 2.4\}$ (Table GA5.6.1-1 [4])

Test situation: $f = \text{MIN}\{R_{p0.2} / 1.5; R_m / 2.4\}$ (Table GA5.6.1-2 [4])

However, the fine element software used for this report (SolidWorks 2019, SP3.0) only show node VON MISES equivalent stresses. Consequently, the admissibility criterion selected in this report is:

- Node VON MISES equivalent stress: $P_N \leq f$

with f the nominal stress for calculation described above in this paragraph.

This situation is conservative.

Note: according to §4, the welding coefficient $z = 0.85$ is applied to admissibility criteria for all the welding in working situation.

6.2 ALLOYS 625 AND 230 CRITERIA

- Alloy 625

The stress criteria in the case of alloy 625 are listed in **Table 8**.

Stress criteria - Alloy 625

Nominal stresses for calculation				
Nominal stress for calculation at test temperature (RT)	f_{625-RT}	$\text{MIN}\{R_{p0.2} / 1.5; R_m / 2.4\}$	278	MPa
Nominal stress for calculation at working temperature (HT)	f_{625-HT}	$\text{MIN}\{R_{p0.2} / 1.5; R_m / 2.4\}$	109	MPa
Test criterion - Test temperature – 22°C				
Node equivalent VON MISES stress	P_N	$P_N \leq f_{625-RT}$	278	MPa
Working criterion - Working temperature – 870°C				
Node equivalent VON MISES stress	P_N	$P_N \leq f_{625-HT}$	109	MPa
Working criterion for welding - Working temperature – 870°C – z = 0.85				
Node equivalent VON MISES stress	P_N	$P_N \leq z \times f_{625-HT}$	92	MPa

Table 8: Stress criteria for alloy 625

- Alloy 230

The stress criteria in the case of alloy 230 are listed in **Table 9**.

Stress criteria - Alloy 230

Nominal stresses for calculation				
Nominal stress for calculation at test temperature (RT)	f_{230-RT}	$\text{MIN}\{R_{p0.2} / 1.5; R_m / 2.4\}$	264	MPa
Nominal stress for calculation at working temperature (HT)	f_{230-HT}	$\text{MIN}\{R_{p0.2} / 1.5; R_m / 2.4\}$	171	MPa
Test criterion - Test temperature – 22°C				
Node equivalent VON MISES stress	P_N	$P_N \leq f_{230-RT}$	264	MPa
Working criterion - Working temperature – 870°C				
Node equivalent VON MISES stress	P_N	$P_N \leq f_{230-HT}$	171	MPa
Working criterion for welding - Working temperature – 870°C – z = 0.85				
Node equivalent VON MISES stress	P_N	$P_N \leq z \times f_{230-HT}$	145	MPa

*Table 9: Stress criteria for alloy 230***7. CREEP**

- Creep criteria

The paragraph GA5.6.1.b of the CODAP [4] gives the formula to estimate the nominal stress for calculation in a normal service situation including material creep. It is expressed as follows:

$$F = \text{MIN} \{ \sigma_R / 1.6; \sigma_{1\%} \}$$

with: σ_R : Stress to obtain failure after 100,000h,

$\sigma_{1\%}$: Stress to obtain 1% strain after 100,000h.

However, experimental data for alloys 625 and 230 are available only up to 10,000h. Consequently, as the solar receiver is considered as an experimental device, the 100,000h creep data have been replaced by 10,000h data. The creep mechanical properties and the creep criteria for both investigated alloys are listed in **Table 10** and in **Table 11**.

Creep criteria - Alloy 625

Creep mechanical properties – 870°C				
Stress to obtain failure after 10,000h	σ_R		10.8	MPa
Stress to obtain 1% strain after 10,000h	$\sigma_{1\%}$		8.6	MPa
Creep nominal stress for calculation at 870°C	$f_{C625-870}$	MIN $\{\sigma_R / 1.6; \sigma_{1\%}\}$	6.8	MPa
Creep working criterion - Working temperature – 870°C				
Node equivalent VON MISES stress	P_N	$P_N \leq f_{C625-870}$	6.8	MPa

*Table 10: Creep criteria for alloy 625 at 870°C***Creep criteria - Alloy 230**

Creep mechanical properties – 870°C				
Stress to obtain failure after 10,000h	σ_R		43	MPa
Stress to obtain 1% strain after 10,000h	$\sigma_{1\%}$		30	MPa
Creep nominal stress for calculation at 870°C	$f_{C230-870}$	MIN $\{\sigma_R / 1.6; \sigma_{1\%}\}$	26.9	MPa
Creep working criterion - Working temperature – 870°C				
Node equivalent VON MISES stress	P_N	$P_N \leq f_{C230-870}$	26.9	MPa

Table 11: Creep criteria for alloy 230 at 870°C

Annex 2: Pressure Vessel analysis concerning the solar receiver – Room temperature results under test pressure**1. TEST PRESSURE**

The test pressure is calculated using the service pressure as follows:

$$P_T = \text{MAX}\{1.43 \times P_S; 1.25 \times P_S \times (f_{\text{alloy-RT}} / f_{\text{alloy-HT}})\}$$

using $f_{\text{alloy-RT}}$ the nominal stress for calculation, which is equal to $\text{MIN}\{R_{p0.2} / 1.5; R_m / 2.4\}$ at test temperature (room temperature) and $f_{\text{alloy-HT}}$ the nominal stress for calculation at working temperature (870°C, Annex 1), service pressure $P_S = 2,5$ bar.

Table 12 gives the test pressure in the case of alloy 625 and alloy 230.

Alloy 625				
Nominal stress for calculation at test temperature (RT)	f_{625-RT}	$\text{MIN}\{R_{p0.2} / 1.5; R_m / 2.4\}$	278	MPa
Nominal stress for calculation at working temperature (HT)	f_{625-HT}	$\text{MIN}\{R_{p0.2} / 1.5; R_m / 2.4\}$	109	MPa
Service pressure	P_S		2.5	bar
Test pressure	P_T	$\text{MAX}\{1.43 \times P_S; 1.25 \times P_S \times (f_{\text{alloy-RT}} / f_{\text{alloy-HT}})\}$	8.0	bar
Alloy 230				
Nominal stress for calculation at test temperature (RT)	f_{230-RT}	$\text{MIN}\{R_{p0.2} / 1.5; R_m / 2.4\}$	264	MPa
Nominal stress for calculation at working temperature (HT)	f_{230-HT}	$\text{MIN}\{R_{p0.2} / 1.5; R_m / 2.4\}$	171	MPa
Service pressure	P_S		2.5	bar
Test pressure	P_T	$\text{MAX}\{1.43 \times P_S; 1.25 \times P_S \times (f_{\text{alloy-RT}} / f_{\text{alloy-HT}})\}$	4.8	bar

Table 12: Test pressure calculation at test temperature for both alloys 625 and 230

As alloy 625 has the biggest difference between its mechanical properties at test and service temperatures, the test pressure is set at 8.0 bar.

2. RESULTS UNDER TEST CONDITIONS (T = 20°C / P = 8 BAR)**2.1 DEFORMATION**

The deformation of the assembly in test situation is shown on **Figure 48**. The maximal deformation in this case is very low: 51µm. It is localized on the inner surface of the assembly near the weld between a centre module manifold and the tube.

Figure 48: Test situation – Total deformation – Cross section (real deformation) showing the weld between the manifolds and the outlet tube (orange line)

2.2 STRESSES

Figure 49 shows the equivalent VON MISES stresses in the complete assembly modelled in the test situation ($T = 20^{\circ}\text{C}$ – $P = 8$ bar). The maximum stress is localized at the closing cap and tube junction with $\sigma = 103.7$ MPa. More precisely, the volume of Ni-based alloy 625 near the junction between the tube and the closing cap showing a stress above 40 MPa is very limited (Figure 50). This maximum stress level is below the stress criterion for both alloys (Node equivalent VON MISES stresses at test temperature, 278 MPa for alloy 625 and 264 MPa for alloy 230, Table 12).

Figure 49: Test situation – VON MISES equivalent stresses in the complete assembly

Figure 50: Test situation – Volume with VON MISES equivalent stress above 40 MPa near the junction between the tube and the closing cap

- **Conclusion**

Modelling the VON MISES equivalent stresses in the assembly in the test situation ($T = 20^{\circ}\text{C}$, $P = 8 \text{ bar}$), low stresses appear in the different part junctions where a weld is made. The maximum stress level (103.7 MPa) is low compared to both alloy stress criteria (alloy 625, $f_{625\text{-RT}} = 278 \text{ MPa}$, alloy 230, $f_{230\text{-RT}} = 264 \text{ MPa}$).